

Profile Questionnaire

*Your name:

*What is your work position?

? Example: Professor, Analyst, Developer, Tester, etc.

*Check the usability evaluation method(s) that you have already participated

! Check all that apply

Heuristic Evaluation

Usability Testing

None

*Check the usability evaluation method(s) that you have already conducted:

! Check all that apply

Heuristic Evaluation

Usability Testing

None

*What is your level of expertise related

	Very poor	Poor	Neutral	Strong	Very strong
to the HCI field?	☐				
to the Usability field?	☐				
to the Heuristic Evaluation field?	☐				